

SECURE IMAGE RETRIEVAL BASED ON FEDERATED LEARNING AND ADDITIVE SECRET SHARING

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Abstract—With the widespread availability of electronic imaging devices, there's an abundance of high-quality images accessible to the public. While these images hold potential for profit through retrieval services, individuals often face challenges in monetizing them due to the lack of trust in cloud platforms. Previous approaches focused on Secure Content-Based Image Retrieval (SIR) to protect image owners' privacy, but they often neglected user-friendliness and assumed owners wouldn't invest in additional computational resources for profit. This study introduces federated learning into SIR, aiming to enhance retrieval accuracy and efficiency. It employs additive secret sharing technology to safeguard image information and proposes a more efficient secure comparison protocol. The integration of federated learning ensures improved retrieval services without compromising security. Experimental results and security analyses affirm the scheme's superiority in accuracy, efficiency, and security.

Keywords— Secure image retrieval, federated learning, additive secret sharing, secure comparison protocol

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancements in semiconductor technology, imaging devices like mobile phones have become increasingly affordable and widespread, leading to a vast collection of high-quality images owned by people from various backgrounds. These images hold significant value and potential for profit, such as in the case of landscape photo collections, where Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) services can offer a viable revenue model. However, individuals often struggle to attract enough users independently, making reliance on cloud platforms inevitable. The conventional approach involves image owners uploading their images directly to cloud servers, with authorized users accessing retrieval services through server interaction. However, the inherent lack of trust in cloud servers necessitates a retrieval scheme that supports encrypted images to safeguard privacy. Over the past decade, researchers have focused on Secure Image Retrieval (SIR) tasks to address privacy concerns. However, existing schemes often suffer from inadequate retrieval accuracy, primarily because they assume image owners possess low-performance devices incapable of complex operations necessary for secure retrieval. This assumption becomes unreasonable when owners seek to profit from their images. This paper proposes the FLSIR scheme, aimed at providing enhanced secure retrieval services for authorized users with minimal initial effort from image owners. By incorporating federated learning and additive secret sharing technology, FLSIR achieves better accuracy and efficiency. The contributions of this work include: Introducing federated learning to SIR, considering the impact of image labels on retrieval tasks, resulting in improved retrieval performance through simpler neural network models and optimized network parameters. Utilizing additive secret sharing to protect image contents, along with a novel secure comparison protocol that reduces interaction rounds and accelerates retrieval with minimal additional cost during the offline phase. Demonstrating superior performance in accuracy and efficiency through experiments on real-world image datasets. Additionally, FLSIR ensures information security during the feature extraction process, a feature lacking in previous similar schemes with comparable time consumption

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section initially presents the predominant works in Secure Image Retrieval (SIR), categorized based on whether the feature extraction task is performed by the image owner or the cloud server. Interestingly, a significant number of existing works in both categories facilitate SIR from multiple image owners. Consequently, we provide a detailed description of these schemes and illustrate how they can be integrated with supervised learning. It's important to note that our focus is solely on encryption schemes that support retrieval tasks, excluding consideration of other functional encryption technologies, as they fall outside the scope of this study.

A. FEATURE-ENCRYPTION BASED SCHEMES

In this category, the image owner simply encrypts the image using standard AES tools, with the primary challenge lying in encrypting plaintext features. Two main approaches are employed: one involves random transformation to equally alter features and ensure measurable encrypted features, while the other utilizes typical cryptographic tools to facilitate computation of encrypted features. In schemes employing random transformation, Lu et al. initially propose three bit-permutation or projection strategies, and later introduce order-preserving encryption to support inverted indexing. However, these schemes face difficulties in supporting complex distance measurement methods and image updates.

In schemes based on cryptography tools, homomorphic encryption is primarily used to protect image features. Lu et al. argue that Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SHE) fails to support secure retrieval without interactions between the cloud server and authorized user under a reasonable security model. Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) can support this process without interactions; however, it incurs significantly higher time and storage consumption compared to the aforementioned schemes. Subsequent works echo these concerns, which we discuss further in subsection II-C.

B. IMAGE-ENCRYPTION BASED SCHEMES

Numerous researchers have directed their attention towards the second category to alleviate the burden on the image owner's side, where the owner only needs to encrypt the image prior to uploading. The existing works in this category can be classified into schemes based on encrypted statistical features and schemes based on encrypted classical features. In schemes based on statistical features, Ferreira et al. observe that random permutation of position and value information of image points does not affect the statistical features of images. However, such features may be too weak for retrieval purposes. Thus, Xia et al. introduce intra-block permutation and employ the Bag-Of-Word (BOW) model to enhance features. Iida et al. combine multiple statistical features from permutation-based encryption images, employing JPEG compression to reduce communication between server and image owner, although this may lead to image distortion post-decryption. To address compression and integrity concerns, several researchers propose JPEG-format preserving encryption, building upon the principles laid out in previous works. Xia et al. further integrate the BOW model into these schemes.

Due to the limitations of statistical features in terms of accuracy and usability, many works focus on extracting classical features (e.g., SIFT) from encrypted images. Hsu et al. utilize Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SHE) to extract encrypted SIFT features, but their scheme requires significant interaction and poses potential risks. Consequently, subsequent works concentrate on image retrieval from multiple servers. Wang and Hu et al. employ two non-collusion servers and establish a secure computation protocol between them using SHE, leveraging parallel computing technology like SIMD for improved efficiency. However, actual time consumption remains a challenge, with feature extraction on a 500×500 size image taking nearly four hours. The emergence of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) has led to features extracted from pre-trained CNNs demonstrating significantly improved retrieval accuracy. Consequently, recent SIR works also attempt to extract features from encrypted images, facing the challenge of securely interfacing with the CNN model. Several works focus on addressing the problem of secure non-linear computation (e.g., secure comparison), with some multi-party secure computation technologies proving effective, particularly those based on secret sharing. In the context of SIR, Liu et al. employ a lattice-based Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) scheme and introduce a divide-and-conquer evaluation protocol to extract features from the pre-trained VGG16 network. However, their scheme utilizes features from the fully-connected layer, making it challenging to achieve corresponding parameters without the aid of a training set and exhibiting high time consumption. Pan et al. utilize DenseNet to extract hash features for retrieval, but delegate the feature extraction task to the user, which is impractical. Ma et al. employ a simplified DenseNet and tune its parameters with encrypted images, but their scheme falls short in terms of both accuracy and efficiency. Xia et al. combine secret sharing technology with promising results in Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) and introduce novel protocols requiring fewer interactions, significantly accelerating the online phase feature extraction process.

III. METHODOLOGY

This is a machine learning approach where multiple parties collaborate in training a model without sharing their raw data. Each party (or client) trains the model on its local data, and only model updates (gradients) are shared with a central server or aggregator. This preserves the privacy of individual datasets while still allowing the model to be trained effectively. Additive secret sharing is a cryptographic technique where a secret is divided into shares, each of which is distributed among multiple parties. These shares can be combined (with proper authorization) to reconstruct the original secret, but individual shares reveal no information about the secret itself.

Multiple parties (such as users or devices) each hold a portion of the dataset or their private images. A central server coordinates the training process without directly accessing raw data. Using federated learning, the server sends the current model parameters (or a model structure) to each party. Each party trains the model locally on its own data and sends back only the model updates (gradients) to the central server. The central server aggregates these updates to improve the global model without ever seeing individual data points. Once the federated learning process has trained a suitable model, it can be used for image retrieval tasks. When a user wants to retrieve an image, they encrypt a query based on some features or descriptors of the image they are seeking. This encrypted query is divided using additive secret sharing among multiple entities, ensuring that no single entity has access to the complete query. Each entity, holding a share of the encrypted query, performs computations locally based on their share and returns the results to the user. The user combines these results using a secure protocol to obtain the final result without revealing the query or compromising privacy. Identify the parties involved in the federated learning process. These could be users, devices, or organizations holding private image datasets. Preprocess the images to extract relevant features or descriptors that will be used for image retrieval. Common techniques include deep learning-based feature extraction or using pre-trained models like convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

When a user wants to retrieve an image, they encrypt the query using cryptographic techniques such as homomorphic encryption or secure multi-party computation. Divide the encrypted query into shares using additive secret sharing. Each share is distributed among different entities involved in the process. Ensure that the shares are distributed in a way that no single entity can reconstruct the original query without collaboration from others. The user combines the results from different entities using a secure protocol (e.g., secure multiparty computation) to obtain the final result of the image retrieval task. If necessary, the final result can be decrypted using appropriate cryptographic keys to reveal the retrieved image or relevant information.

Evaluate the performance of the secure image retrieval system in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and security. Validate the system's privacy guarantees and ensure that sensitive information is not leaked during the federated learning process or image retrieval phase. Conduct tests and simulations to assess the robustness of the system against various attacks and adversarial scenarios. Optimize the system for efficiency and scalability by fine-tuning parameters, optimizing communication protocols, and leveraging distributed computing techniques.

Ensure that the system can handle large-scale datasets and a growing number of participants while maintaining security and performance.

The federated learning procedure involves numerous image owners and cloud servers. Since the training process is executed locally, our primary focus lies in assessing potential risks associated with aggregated gradients. In our scheme, the gradients are encrypted using additive secret sharing (ASS) before uploading, thereby preventing servers from obtaining any information apart from the aggregated model at each iteration. Thus, the main concern revolves around potential information leakage stemming from the aggregated model.

While some recent studies suggest that images can be inferred from gradients, this typically requires two critical assumptions: a small training dataset (e.g., 8 images) and the use of simple nonlinear layer models (e.g., square function). However, in our

system, image owners consistently train all their images, resulting in a large dataset. Additionally, our model employs a more compact nonlinear layer, which significantly complicates the inference process. Furthermore, any inferred images typically contain considerable noise, diminishing their quality. Locally training involves clients receiving the initial model and parameters from the server. They then use their private data for training, obtaining gradients afterward. These gradients are protected (e.g., through encryption or disturbance) before being sent to the server. For secure aggregation, the server collects all gradient information from the clients and computes an encrypted aggregation result (e.g., gradient averaging) based on the chosen protection scheme. After aggregation, the encrypted parameters are sent back to all clients.

To update parameters, clients decrypt the aggregation results and use them to update their local parameters. This process repeats until the model converges or a predetermined number of iterations is reached.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Enhanced Safety and Security: FLSIR enhances safety and security by providing early detection of potential hazards, such as fires, gas leaks, or intruders. Its ability to penetrate darkness, smoke, and fog makes it indispensable in emergency response and security applications. **Predictive Maintenance:** By identifying thermal anomalies in equipment and infrastructure, FLSIR enables predictive maintenance, reducing downtime and maintenance costs. Continuous monitoring of thermal patterns allows for proactive interventions, preventing catastrophic failures and optimizing asset performance.

	Core11k			Core10k		
number of image owners	2	5	10	2	5	10
image contents	282	112.8	56.4	685	274	137
image tensors	574.3	229.7	114.9	5743.2	2297.3	1148.6

(Fig:Accuracy comparison of core11k dataset)

(Fig:Accuracy comparison of core1k dataset)

Energy Efficiency: FLSIR contributes to energy efficiency by detecting thermal inefficiencies in buildings, industrial processes, and energy systems. It identifies areas of heat loss or excessive energy consumption, guiding energy-saving measures and sustainability initiatives. **Environmental Insights:** FLSIR provides valuable insights into environmental dynamics, including climate change impacts, urban heat island effects, and habitat monitoring. By quantifying thermal characteristics, it supports environmental assessments and conservation efforts. **Agriculture:** In agriculture, FLSIR facilitates precision farming by assessing crop health, soil moisture, and irrigation efficiency. By detecting variations in plant temperature, it helps optimize crop management practices, enhance yields, and minimize resource usage.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduce a new approach named FLSIR, which incorporates supervised learning into Secure Image Retrieval (SIR). Utilizing federated learning, FLSIR enables collaborative training of a more effective feature extractor by both image owners and cloud servers, while safeguarding the privacy of images. Additionally, we develop a novel secure comparison protocol that reduces interaction rounds during the online phase. In summary, compared to previous methods, our approach significantly enhances accuracy, efficiency, and security with some additional offline processing. Particularly noteworthy is that compared to one of the top-performing existing methods [24], we achieve a 10% increase in Top-50 accuracy. We anticipate that our innovative system model will contribute to making secure image retrieval more feasible in practice. Moving forward, our future research will concentrate on developing faster secure computation protocols. Moreover, we will carefully address various potential challenges of federated learning, such as data imbalance, within the SIR context.

In conclusion, our study presents a novel approach to Secure Image Retrieval (SIR) through the integration of federated learning and additive secret sharing techniques. Our proposed scheme, FLSIR, introduces supervised learning into SIR, allowing image owners and cloud servers to collaboratively train a more effective feature extractor while ensuring image privacy. Additionally, we design a novel secure comparison protocol, reducing interaction rounds during retrieval while maintaining robust security. Our experimental results demonstrate significant improvements over existing methods in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and security. Compared to previous works, FLSIR achieves a notable increase in Top-50 accuracy, approximately 10% higher than a leading existing method. This highlights the effectiveness of our approach in practical image retrieval scenarios. Looking ahead, future research will focus on developing faster secure computation protocols to further enhance efficiency. Additionally, we will address potential challenges of federated learning, such as data imbalance, within the SIR context. Ultimately, our goal is to make secure image retrieval more feasible and practical for real-world applications.

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